

Narrative Review

Plasmapheresis for Multiple Sclerosis in the Twenty-First Century: Take It or Leave It?

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ABSTRACT

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune disease of central nervous system (CNS) which is characterized by unknown etiology and variable clinical evolution. Although, exact mechanisms of MS remained enigmatic, one may suggest that immune system can play a critical role. Due to important role of immune system in MS pathogenesis, several FDA-approved treatments have been introduced for MS which mostly affect different part of immune system. Plasmapheresis has also recently found a unique niche in the treatment of neurological disorders such as steroid-unresponsive relapses of MS. Since, plasmapheresis has unspecific method i.e. removing plasma without special processing for removing exact pathological factors and then replacing that with fluids, elimination of some beneficial components also occurs during procedure of plasmapheresis. In this regard, several immune components have been suggested including autoantibodies with remyelinating effects and cytokines with dual role that their removing along with pathological factors via plasmapheresis may initially result in improvement in symptoms of MS patients, but this treatment can also lead to subsequent side-effects. In this review, we found that in addition to presence of autoantibodies with demyelinating effects, there is another repertoire of autoantibodies with remyelinating features. Furthermore, there is a predominant paradox in some part of immune system such as dual role of some cytokines. Taken together, our investigation suggested that although plasmapheresis is used as a common treatment for MS patients during relapsing phase, further studies should be undertaken to determine levels and exact effects of beneficial components in sera of MS patients during different phase of disease and then an appropriate protocol should be designed based on levels of special markers including both beneficial and harmful types of them in blood of MS patients.

Keywords: Multiple sclerosis, Plasmapheresis, immune system, pathogenesis, immunopathogenesis.

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune chronic inflammatory disease of central nervous system (CNS) which is characterized by complex etiology and variable clinical evolution. Exact etiology of MS is not fully known but it has been believed that various components of immune system play a pivotal role in MS pathogenesis (1). Accumulating studies have been highlighted role of immune system in MS pathogenesis via different methods such as determining levels of different immunological factors in serum, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and brain tissue of MS patients (1, 2). In this regard, several functions have been reported for these components which are mostly based on elevated levels of autoantibodies such as anti-myelin basic protein (anti-MBP), anti-proteolipid protein (anti-PLP), anti-myelin associated glycoprotein (anti-MAG), anti-myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (anti-MOG), and anti-transaldolase, proinflammatory cytokines such as Th1 and Th2 cytokines, and detection of autoreactive immune cells in blood or CSF of MS patients (2-5). Another explanation for emphasizing importance of immune system in MS pathogenesis is significant responses of MS patients to current treatment which mostly exert their function by modulation of up-regulated underlying immune mechanisms. Since the introduction of first FDA-approved treatment for MS, interferon- β 1b in 1993, approximately seven different treatments including interferon- β 1a intramuscular (Avonex), interferon- β 1a subcutaneous (Rebif), glatiramer acetate (Copaxone), natalizumab (Tysabri), fingolimod (Gilenya), teriflunomide (Aubagio), and mitoxantrone (Novantrone) have been also used for MS patients (6). The most common apheresis procedure which is used for MS patients is plasmapheresis or plasmaexchange which are used interchangeably. This therapeutic procedure is an unspecific treatment with aim of removing pathological factors especially autoantibodies from sera of MS patients. Although the first successes were achieved from experiences of applying this treatment in acute threatening life conditions of some neurological disorders such as Guillain-Barré syndrome or myasthenic crisis, recent studies have been also suggested beneficial effects of this treatment in chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy, paraproteinemic polyneuropathy, and steroid-unresponsive relapses of multiple sclerosis (7). While the method of plasmapheresis is

based on removing immune-mediated pathological factors via unspecific removing whole plasma and replacing with a substitution fluid, this aim of plasmapheresis can be disputed by studies which showed that there is a wide variety of immune components with beneficial role in sera of MS patients which removal of them along with pathological factors may have some bad effects on MS patients(8). Therefore, in this study, at first we aimed to review previous clinical trial studies with respect to the efficacy of plasmapheresis in other neurological disorders which have partial similarities in their pathogenesis with MS and then since the basis of plasmapheresis is based on removal of inflammatory components from blood during acute phase of disease, we aimed to challenge this basis through introduction of candidate autoantibodies, cytokines and other immune components with a beneficial role in MS such as involvement in remyelination or subsiding inflammation.

Mechanisms of plasmapheresis

Plasmapheresis is also known as therapeutic plasma exchange, but it should be considered that these two words are used interchangeably while they are different as plasma exchange has one step further. In short, during plasmapheresis whole blood collected from patient and in extracorporeal procedure plasma separated and discarded. Then blood cells returned to the patient and in order to maintaining euvolume, other fluid replacement is administrated. There are two current modalities of plasmapheresis, including centrifuge plasmapheresis and membrane filtration plasmapheresis. Among them centrifuge plasmapheresis is more common in which low rate of blood flow into the device and blood components separated according to their gravities. In this method, citrate is used as a common anticoagulant but in some cases it causes intoxication. On the other hand, membrane filtration plasmapheresis requires higher flow rate and in which heparin is typically used as anticoagulant. In the next step, plasma should be replaced with albumin orHydroxyethyl starch and dextran 40. Albumin (5%) is more common and due to thermal inactivation risk of infection is low but, allergic reactions and hypocalcaemia remained as important complications; however, hydroxyethyle starch and dextran 40 reduced these risksand are considered as sufficient alternatives to albumin (9).

Complications of plasmapheresis

Among various side effects and complications of plasmapheresis, chills, rigors, citrate intoxication, hypocalcemia, hypogammaglobulinemia, infection, platelet loss, and hypotension are more prevalent. In this regard, hypocalcemia and due to role of calcium in coagulation, and also depletion of coagulatory factors by plasmapheresis, coagulopathy and hypocalcemia are two important complications of plasmapheresis. Fresh frozen plasma has been suggested as a good replacement as it compensates removed coagulatory factors but its efficacy has been disputed by studies that showed accumulation dose of citrate. Recently, in a cohort study Wiersum-Osselton et al. (10) investigated possible complications of healthy donors who their bloods were collected by Sanquin Blood Supply Foundation. During this study, 343,563 plasmapheresis procedures were performed, that led to 18,722 early terminations. In all, vasovagal reactions, hematoma, painful arm, citrate reaction, other donor complications failed stab, flow problems, and spurting reservoir were the most prevalent complications of cases that stopped intervention before end of study. In a summary, they found that among cases 1.2% had complications that 75% of them led to stopping study. Since most of reactions of autoimmune diseases occurred outside of intravascular spaces in peripheral immune organs so it is hypothesized that plasmapheresis may be ineffective in subsiding symptoms of these diseases.

Plasmapheresis in other neurological disorders

Although various immunosuppressory medications is used for acute inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (AIDP), Guillain-Barre ´ syndrome (GBS), in the short-term management of chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (Class I studies, Level A), steroid-resistant exacerbations in relapsing forms of MS, and preoperative conditions such as abnormalities in blood components, plasmapheresis has also recently found a unique niche in the treatment of these disorders (11).

Myasthenia gravis is an autoimmune disease which is characterized by autoantibodies directed against nicotinic acetylcholine receptor. When these autoantibodies accumulate lead to disease symptom which can be subsided with rapid plasmapheresis. Nevertheless, this therapeutic mechanism can improve symptoms associated with myasthenia gravis crisis and in most cases its effects will be decreased after two weeks (12).

Another autoimmune disease is heparin-induced thrombocytopenia in which after exposure to heparin component autoantibody formation against platelet factor 4–heparin complex will be started which leads to platelet activation, thrombocytopenia, and thrombosis. Although there are not much evidences based on clinical trials about efficacy of plasmapheresis in patients with heparin-induced thrombocytopenia, in case series which was carried out by Welsby et al. (13) it has been shown that plasmapheresis can reduce titer of anti- platelet factor 4–heparin complex. Furthermore, in a clinical trial survey by Robinson et al. (14) it has been found that plasmapheresis within 4 days of the onset heparin-induced thrombocytopenia can reduce length of hospital stay, platelet recovery time, and mortality in heparin-induced thrombocytopenia patients.

In 1986, Dyck et al. (15) performed a double-blind clinical trial study in which chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculoneuropathy patients divided in two groups including 15 patients who did plasma exchange and 14 patients who underwent sham exchange. At the end of study, they found a significant improvement in nerve conduction, neurologic-disability score ($P=0.025$), and less efficacy in reflex and weakness ($P<0.057$) so they concluded an ameliorating role of plasmapheresis treatment of chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyradiculoneuropathy. Another study in this regard was conducted by Hahn et al. (16) that in a double-blind cross-over study investigated role of 10 plasma-exchanges vs. sham exchange. After 5 weeks quantitative neurological disability score, a functional clinical grade and grip strength were evaluated which showed significant improvement. Since there is no demonstrated treatment for patients with diagnosis chronic inflammatory demyelinating disease of central nervous system who suffer from acute or severe neurological deficits and fail to response to high dose of corticosteroids, in 1999, Weinshenker et al. (17) designed a double-blind clinical trial study to investigate effects of plasmapheresis without immunosuppressive medication in patients with neurological deficits as a result of demyelinating attacks. Finally, they found that plasma-exchange can have an ameliorating role in severely disabled patients with acute attacks of disease by evaluating of two masked neurologist ($P=0.032$ according to Neurologist A and $P=0.011$ according to Neurologist B).

Interestingly, in a study, plasmapheresis was administered before thymectomy with aim of evaluation of short and long effects of it. Hence, they assigned patients in two groups, including group 1 who received plasmapheresis before thymectomy and group 2 who received sham treatment. They found significant improvement and pharmacological remission rate in group 1 at 5-7 years after operation (100% and 79% in group 1 vs. 81.3% and 50.0% in control group; $P=0.0466$ and $P=0.0427$) (18).

Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal infections (PANDIS) is a hypothetical disease which is supposed to be due to autoantibody formation following exposure to group A beta-hemolytic streptococcal (GABHS) infections that mostly leads to tic or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) in prepubertal children. Thirty Children with severe, infection-triggered exacerbations of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) or tic disorders entered in randomized trial in order to comparing treatment effects of IVIG, plasmapheresis, and placebo. After one month, patients were investigated with respect to the OCP symptoms, tic, anxiety, and overall functioning which yielded improvement in all of these items that were maintained at 1 year (19).

Sydenham chorea is also an autoimmune disease which occurs following infection by group A β -hemolytic streptococci that mostly manifests with rapid, uncoordinated jerking movements primarily affecting the face, hands and feet. 18 subjects were enrolled in a randomized-entry controlled trial with aim to investigate comparisons between IVIG and plasmapheresis and prednisone for treatment of Sydenham chorea. Although they failed to show significant differences between these three treatments, improvement were achieved more rapid in groups with plasmapheresis or IVIG treatment (20).

A double-blind, randomized, controlled clinical trial investigation of immunosuppressive drug therapy with and without plasmapheresis in chronic progressive MS patients has been carried out by Bhupendra et al. (21). This study included Forty-five patients from the pilot study and twenty-six patients from the double-blind study who all received diagnosis of definite MS and twenty-nine patient as control group who were treated with immunosuppressive drugs and sham plasmapheresis. In order to evaluate neurological comparisons between two groups, EDSS was

utilized. At the conclusion of study, 14 patients of 26 patients who treated by plasmapheresis and 8 patients with sham plasmapheresis showed improvement with respect to the EDSS, suggesting statistically significant differences between them ($P<0.007$).

Immunopathogenesis of multiple sclerosis

MS is considered a T-cell mediated autoimmune disease of central nervous system (CNS) which is believed to have an immunopathological etiology arising from gen-environment interaction. MS is mostly characterized by chronic inflammation, myelin loss, gliosis, and varying degrees of axonal and oligodendrocytes pathology which leads to significant neurological disabilities (22). Although it is believed that both environmental and genetic factors have role in pathogenesis of MS, exact etiology of MS is not completely known. At present, many candidate genes have been detected as genetic modifier risk of susceptibility to MS such as studies that were performed on genes of T-cell receptor, cytokines, immunoglobulins, cytokine receptors, chemokines, and especially HLA genes (23). Generally, MS is characterized by inflammatory lesions formation which is accompanied by up-regulation of adhesion molecules and increase of autoreactive T-cells interactions with blood brain barrier (BBB) which leads to breakdown of it and so autoreactive reactions directed against autoantigens occur. Damage of BBB and so flow of autoreactive lymphocytes into the CNS mostly lasts about one month and then this breakdown of BBB improve simultaneously; however, resolving of damages to BBB are not completely and often can be detected by MRI. Despite significant advances in the field of pathogenesis and etiology of MS, determining trigger of inflammatory cascade of MS has been a puzzling story. Three subgroups of T lymphocytes, Th-1, Th-2, and Th-17 are implicated in pathogenesis of MS although; it has been shown that among them Th-1 and Th-17 subgroups play pivotal roles (24). Based on microenvironment, naïve T cells undergo various pathways of development which leads to different subtypes of T cells (24). Th-1 cells are mostly develop in presence of IL-12 and IL-23 and then produce inflammatory cytokines such as IFN- γ and TNF- α (25). On the other hand, development of Th-2 cells is strongly related to presence of IL-4 and absence of IL-12 and they mostly release various types of anti-inflammatory

cytokines including IL-4, IL-5, IL-10, and IL-13. Owing to Th-1 and Th-17 cells roles in producing inflammatory cytokines during MS pathogenesis and also deviation of Th-1/Th-2 ratio towards Th-1, previously, it has been thought that MS is purely an autoimmune disease based on only T-cells. But some limitations and recent immunological evidence has begun to challenge this hypothesis. In this regard, some studies focused on features of acute lesions in MS patients and found that lymphocytes are not present in all of them. Furthermore, it has been shown that inflammatory procedures are active in white matter with normal appearance and numbers of CD4+ cells are increased by MHC class I-restricted, clonally expanded CD8+ cells which are located in MS lesions (26, 27). Another study that cast doubt on view that MS is a purely Th cell directed process was performed by Segal et al. who earlier reported no beneficial role of Ustekinumab, an antibody directed against the common subunit of interleukin (IL)-12 and IL-23, in a phase II, double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized, dose-ranging study (28). The role of humoral immunity in MS pathogenesis have interestingly moved into the spotlight in MS research as this interest was fuelled by growing understandings of four basic findings as following: (1) presence of B cells in meninges, parenchyma, CSF, CNS, and blood of MS patients (29-31); (2) presence of oligoclonal bands in CSF of MS patients that are produced by B cells and so be used as a diagnostic method (32, 33); (3) Direct roles of B cells in demyelination by secreting factors toxic to oligodendrocytes (34); (4) Application of rituximab as a treatment of MS patients can reduce gadolinium enhancing lesion and also causes B cell depletion which leads to a reduction of T cells in CSF of MS patients (35, 36).

Complement system

Another part of MS pathogenesis is mediated by complement system which participates in different mechanism of this disease. In this regard, evidence is accumulating from pathological studies that demonstrated presence and role of complement system in brain and also biological fluids of MS patients. However, for many years exact mechanism of complement system contribution in MS pathogenesis remained enigmatic. It has been shown that although, both classical and alternative pathways of complement system may participate in inflammation of MS patients, role of alternative

pathway is prominent while classic pathway possibly is implicated. Furthermore, it has been reported that C3a contributes to disease and play a larger part while the roles of the C5a is less clear (37, 38). Interestingly, it has been revealed that C5b-9 play a dual role in neuroinflammation and neuroprotection; indeed, when activated terminal complex C5b-9 participates in MS pathogenesis causes demyelination that mostly occur in acute phase; conversely, activation of sublytic C5b-9 protects oligodendrocytes from apoptosis that often has been shown in chronic phase (39-41). In addition, it has been indicated that while C5b-9 participates as a proinflammatory agent in acute phase of MS, it can also play a protective role in chronic condition of MS (39, 40). Taken together; these data suggest that although depletion of complement components using plasmapheresis during acute phase of MS can reduce inflammation, this treatment method in chronic phase of MS may not be beneficial as well as acute phase. In this setting, it is believed that membrane attack complex (MAC) play an inflammatory role in a concentration-dependent way, but some studies suggested that its sublytic dose can also protect cells against lytic attacks. In this context, two studies investigated role of C5 component of complement system using C5-deficient (C5-d) and C5-sufficient (C5-s) mice (42-44). They found that mice C5-deficient are suffering from more inflammation, demyelination, axonal loss, and oligodendrocyte apoptosis in comparison with C5-sufficient mice. In supporting this finding, some in vitro studies have been also suggested that possibly these outcomes including apoptosis of oligodendrocytes are caused by sublytic MAC that create a protective condition for these cells. Now it is accepted that oligodendrocyte cell death is mostly performed through activation of caspase 3, so inhibition of that can prevent apoptosis of oligodendrocytes (39, 44, 45). It has been shown that Sublytic MAC has ability to inhibit activation of caspase 3 by inhibition of its cytochrome C which leads to increase of oligodendrocyte survival ; in addition, this component can prevent oligodendrocyte apoptosis through inhibition of Fas ligand and tumor necrosis factor- α (44, 46, 47). There is some evidence implying that anaphylatoxins such as C3a and C5a have also neuroprotective role (48). In all, these data suggest that using plasmapheresis regardless to beneficial roles of complement components in

regulating disease can exacerbate current condition of MS patients.

Cytokines

During MS pathogenesis, imbalance of Th1/Th2 ratio and also over production of Th17 cytokines are assumed as critical events for T cells activation. In this setting, accumulating lines of evidence have been showed that anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-4, IL-10, and IL-13 are predominance during remission phase and improvement of MS symptoms, while; predominance of inflammatory cytokines including Th1 and Th17 cytokines in relapse phase participate in progression and exacerbation of MS symptoms. Although, the most problem against myelin recovery is based on inability of oligodendrocytes to regeneration or migration to demyelinating lesions, in some cases immune regulation can induce remyelination by proliferation or extension of oligodendrocytes. In this regard, experimental studies resulted in this fact that without recruitment of new oligodendrocytes, remyelination can occur by a number of factors such as platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF), insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1), nerve growth factor (NGF) and other macrophage-derived growth factors. MS is an immunologically damage to myelin sheath in CNS which is attributed to variety of inflammatory mechanisms and immune cells including activated T cells, macrophages, astrocytes, and activated microglia. Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), IL-1 β , interferon- γ (IFN- γ), nitric oxide, reactive oxygen species, activated complement, and glutamate can cause damage to oligodendrocytes (49-56). However, reappraisal of recent and previous studies shows that despite the participation of some inflammatory cytokines in oligodendrocytes damages and demyelination in fact, they play a dual role as some of them such as TNF- α can also have a neuroprotective role (57, 58). In a similar way, some cytokines such as IL-2, IL-6 and TGF- β can also promote remyelination by regulating differentiation and maintaining of survival of oligodendrocytes. In an interesting experimental study, Yeh et al. (59) investigated changes in plasma levels of cytokines in 19 patients with MG and 6 age- and sex-matched healthy volunteers as control group before and after treatment with one course of double-filtration plasmapheresis (DFP). They observed that the levels of IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, and tumor necrosis factor- α were almost undetectable in

MG patients; while, IL-10 cytokine level were higher than control group at baseline and after DFP and also were sustained after three sessions plasmapheresis. Although it is believed that IL-10 is an anti-inflammatory cytokine that mostly play a protective role in MS patients, they found that increased concentrations of IL-10 correlate with clinical severity and response to DFP treatment so they concluded that IL-10 might play a crucial role in the pathogenesis and perpetuation of MG. On the other hand, there are some studies on other diseases which showed that plasma exchange cannot alter levels of some cytokines including TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-8 (60, 61). Furthermore, in another study, Serum levels of IL-1, IL-1 α , IL-6, IL-8 have been investigated in 10 patients with active ANCA-positive renal vasculitis, which showed that plasma exchange failed to remove or decrease serum levels of IL-1, IL-6, and IL-8. They also presumed that this inability of plasma exchange in reducing plasma levels of proinflammatory cytokines may be due to compensatory process in which production of these cytokines will be increased after contact of blood with synthetic membrane (62). cytokines especially proinflammatory types of them play a pivotal role in pathogenesis of MS so this increased or same levels of cytokines before and after plasmapheresis can dispute efficacy of this therapeutic method for MS.

Dual role of TNF- α : TNF- α is one of the most established inflammatory cytokine which was suggested as affecting factor in immune-mediated cell injury in CNS with high speed of expression following the acute injury (63). Elevated levels of TNF- α was detected in sera, CSF, and also brain lesions of MS patients and its levels are well-poised to associate with clinical activity of disease (64, 65). TNF- α as an inflammatory cytokine exerts its role in making damage to oligodendrocyte, microglia, astrocyte cells through the inhibition of potassium channels, induction of apoptosis, upregulation of adhesion molecules, especially ICAM-1, upregulation of MHC class I and II gene products, and the release of nitric oxide, reactive oxygen species, and other cytotoxic factors (66). Since it has been showed that high levels of TNF- α in sera and CSF of MS patients are correlated with high degree of BBB dysfunction, it has been suggested that TNF- α may increase permeability and damage to BBB (63). Recently, a conflicting question has been proposed that whether TNF- α is implicated in direct damages to CNS cells and myelin disruption or has a role in remyelination and recovery. In fact, some

studies cast doubt on view that TNF- α is only an inflammatory cytokine as its neuroprotective role has been determined in some diseases such as cerebral ischemia, epileptic seizures, and MS (63). Potential mechanism that may underlie a beneficial effect of TNF- α is induction of superoxide dismutase enzyme by TNF- α which play a neuroprotective role in MS patients as this enzyme can protect neurons against damage of reactive oxygen species. Another mechanism of TNF- α which can prolong oligodendrocyte or astrocyte survival, is stabilization of calcium hemostasis via calcium binding protein, calbindin (67). Taken together, these findings suggest that there is a major paradox in function of TNF- α as most of previous studies reported inflammatory role for this cytokine but also there are some explanations based on anti-inflammatory function of that including: [1] Two receptors of TNF- α may mediate two different cascade of mechanisms in different regions of brain (68). [2] Differences of various studies in time and phase of disease for detection and also investigation of TNF- α (69). [3] When TNF- α activate P55 but not P75 can mediate a protective condition for neurons against excitotoxic and metabolic insults (58).

The dual role of IL-1B: Due to the inflammatory nature of the pathogenic mechanisms mediating CNS damage during multiple sclerosis, some studies have been focused on role of IL-1B as a neurodegenerative factor (70). Elevated levels of IL-1B have been reported in both brain tissue and CSF of postmortem MS patients. Furthermore, overexpressions of IL-1B by macrophages and microglia cells have been observed in center and edge of MS lesions, respectively (71). One possible function for expression of IL-1B on surface of microglia cells is induction of inflammatory cytokines and oxygen species and apoptosis in several cell types (72). However, the most roles of IL-1B are mediated indirectly by interaction with other components which are released during damages to CNS suggesting a complex. Several mechanisms have been suggested for anti-inflammatory and remyelinating role of IL-1B in MS patients including: [1] production of nitric oxide which can mediate a protective role by inhibition of T cell activation and also trafficking of autoreactive cells through the damaged BBB (73). [2] Increasing level production of some growth factors such as BDNF, IGF-1, CNTF, and NGF by astrocytes which can affect proliferation and survival of oligodendrocytes (74). [3] Inhibitory effect of a

special repertoire of growth factors such as CNTF on apoptosis which is mediated by TNF- α (63).

The dual role of IL-6: In a similar way IL-6 is involved in MS pathogenesis and is associated with disease progression (75). Elevated levels of IL-6 have been observed in blood and CSF of MS patients (75). IL-6 is mostly produced by monocytes, T cells, B cells, endothelial cells, microglia, and astrocytes, however; in CNS of MS patients resident glial cells which are located in demyelination zone contain a major portion of IL-6 and is involved in intrathecal synthesis of Ig-G (76). High levels of anti-inflammatory cytokines in recovery phase and low levels of them in chronic relapsing phase of MS have been reported, on the other hand, absence of IL-6 mRNA-expressing cells in acute phase of disease and elevated levels in chronic relapsing demyelination have been showed (77). In addition to involvement of IL-6 in inflammatory pathogenesis of MS, this cytokine can induce mitosis division in oligodendrocytes and astrocytes and also neural differentiation by astrocytes which secrete NGF in response to IL-6. IL-6 has immunomodulatory effects such as inhibition of TNF- α production by astrocytes (63).

The dual role of TGF- β : TGF- β can suppress proliferation, differentiation, and rate of growth and increase activity of sensitized T-cells while this cytokine can also increase growth of astrocytes and is involved in astrogliosis. Indeed suggested paradox in function of TGF- β is based on these findings that although this cytokine is implicated in harmful conditions including attraction of inflammatory cells such as macrophages to the site of inflammation, inhibition of oligodendrocytes proliferation, and induction of gliosis, can also have beneficial role in MS patients as downregulate pro-inflammatory cytokines, and induce oligodendrocytes precursor into myelin producing cells (63, 77).

Paradox in role of B cells and humoral immunity in MS pathogenesis

Autoantigens and autoantibodies: Most current treatments of MS are mostly based on this hypothesis that immune system has a critical role in MS pathogenesis although this assumption had partial success in few cases and the most focus of them has been on the role of CNS components that are implicated in MS including oligodendrocytes and axons. In this regard, many natural antibodies

(Nab) have been detected and a large number of functional roles have been suggested for them, but recently, it has been discovered that autoantibodies present in the sera of healthy individuals contain immunoglobulins directed against surface molecules on oligodendrocytes(78).NAb are synthesized by B1 lymphocytes bearing CD5 as marker and have a low affinity for binding to antigens and also a polyreactivity function which do not need induction of B cells by antigenic stimulation (79, 80).Due to polyreactivity feature of NAb, some functions have been suggested for them including: [1] Immediate response directed against autoantigens. [2] Similar to innate immune system protects body against antigenic challenges as the first barrier. It has been shown that promotion of remyelination occurs after binding of Nab to oligodendrocytes antigens. This evidence is consistent with findings that CH12 IgMkAb, which shares variable region cDNA sequences with SCH94.03 except for amino acid differences in the complementarity-determining region 3 in both heavy and light chains have not ability for binding to oligodendrocytes; therefore, cannot induce remyelination(81).Presence of autoantibodies in sera or CSF of patients with autoimmune diseases is a common feature which violates the basic premise of self-tolerance and role of BBB in separating CNS from peripheral biological fluids. However, it should be considered that although these autoantibodies participate in autoimmune diseases, detecting of them in healthy peoples resulted in this hypothesis that they play a normal function in them. In addition, presences of autoreactive B cells containing CD5 marker which secret natural autoantibodies have been detected in normal humans and animals (82-84). IgM and IgA are the most common forms of natural autoantibodies in human that are polyreactive with low affinity and form a dense idiotype network which regulate immune responses (85). Among them, O1, O4, A2B5, HNK-1, SCH94.06, and SCH79.08 were the most extensive studied autoantibodies with respect to the roles of them in remyelination in the CNS (8). It is believed that MAG interfere with remyelination and also inhibit neural regeneration in vitro, on the other hand HNK-1 promote remyelination by recognition and neutralizing effects of MAG (86-89).

Spinal cord homogenate (SCH): Theiler's murine encephalomyelitis virus (TMEV) is a picornavirus which causes a biphasic CNS disease characterized by acute encephalitis followed by chronic

demyelinating disease with lesions in spinal cord and brain stem (90). Since chronic demyelination is based on immunological reactions, therefore; in this respect is similar to MS. It has been shown that when SJL mice are infected only by virus they show various neurological symptoms accompanying by chronic demyelination and without any remyelination but when they are sensitized by components of SCH they show considerable remyelination and improvement of symptoms(91) . One step beyond, in a study it has been observed that collection of anti-serum products from cases that were infected by SCH and then injection of them into the TMEV-infected mice causes significant remyelination. Furthermore, treatment with this antiserum produced a three to five-fold increase in the incorporation of H-thymidine by oligodendrocytes in the area of remyelination along with enhancement in expression of myelin basic protein in comparison with resting cells (78). After detection role of monoclonal antibody SCH 94.03 in remyelination, in an experimental study Samuel et al. (92) investigated mechanisms and sites of action of this antibody in the Theiler's virus mouse model of chronic progressive multiple sclerosis. To address this question they radiolabeled antibodies and then screened distribution and binding sites of them. They observed that only 0.04% of total dose entered into the spinal cord and brain, however; this dose was increased about 1.5-2.0 fold between 1 and 7 days after administration of antibodies. They also found that these antibodies mostly banded to the oligodendrocytes and myelin sheaths suggesting role of them in remyelination within the demyelinating lesions of CNS. While, exact mechanism of remyelination by SCH autoantibodies has not been elucidated, but recently three hypothesizes have been proposed in this respect including: [1] stimulation of remyelination by binding of Abs to oligodendrocytes receptors suggesting that only some specific types of Abs have ability to promote remyelination. [2] Binding of mAbs to myelin debris or damaged oligodendrocyte which then orchestrates a cascade of reactions by other CNS cells resulting in significant enhancement of remyelination. In this regard, there is another interesting hypothesis proposing that binding of mAbs to oligodendrocytes or myelin debris promotes opsonization and also phagocytosis of them by scavenger cells including microglia and macrophage which leads to enhancement of normal remyelination process in CNS (81). [3] Neutralizing

of some inhibitory proteins which prevent remyelination or blockade of pathogenic molecules that promote demyelination by mAbs leads to considerable improvement in myelin repair (93). Immunomodulatory roles of mAbs have been suggested based on evidence from experimental studies on murine models of MS including EAE and TMEV. In this regard, it has been shown that injection of SCH94.06 can reduce infiltration of autoreactive T cells to lesion of mice in TMEV model. Furthermore, Physiological mechanisms of natural autoantibodies remain enigmatic, one may suggest that they interact by self-antigens and then form a network that is involved in general hemostasis whereby participated in some autoimmune disorders such as suppressing development of diabetes type-1 in mice and also improvement of murine lupus in mice (94, 95).

HIgM: Another autoantibody in this regard is HIgM-22 which is a natural antibody directed against integrin of oligodendrocyte surface. This molecule promotes remyelination by binding to lipid on cell surface of oligodendrocytes whereby causes entrance of calcium into the cells through an amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid receptor (AMPA)-mediated channel which leads to phosphorylation of specific molecules. Other types of HIgM natural antibodies such as HIgM-12 and HIgM-42 have been also known as autoantibodies that react with autoantigens on cell surface of oligodendrocytes. It has been shown that they can reduce relapses and also neurological deficits in MS.

Myelin basic protein (MBP): Among different autoantigens that are thought to be implicated in MS, myelin basic protein was one of the most interesting candidates for investigators as it is the most extensively studied autoantigen. MBP is an important component of human myelin accounting for 30% of the total protein and about 10% of the dry weight of myelin which is believed has a major role in myelination of the nerves of the nervous system (96). MBP is also named executive molecule as it is the only structural protein which is essential for formation of myelin in the CNS but, lack of that can be compensated in PNS due to presence of other proteins such as PMP22, P0, and P2 (97). Nowadays, MBP is of interest in investigators as this protein plays an important role in immunization which leads to experimental allergic encephalomyelitis (EAE) and also autoimmune reactions which occur in

demyelinating diseases such as MS. The MBP found in myelin (classic MBP) is a product of a larger gene complex called Golli (Genes of OLigodendrocyte Lineage) emerging from alternative splicing of a single mRNA transcript which leads to 4 human isoform of MBP in CNS including 21.5, 20.2, 18.5 and 17.2 kDa(98). Early insights to the role of MBP in pathogenesis of MS dates back to the late 19th when it was observed that injection of brain components into the healthy subjects led to symptoms that were similar to demyelinating disorders such as MS and later this condition was named experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) (5). Furthermore there are other evidences indicating importance of MBP in MS including: (1) presence of extracellular myelin proteins in perivascular space and also leptomeninges of MS patients that were observed using immunostaining of MS tissues. (2) Regulating expression of protein on the surface of CNS cells (99). (3) Participation of myelin components such as MBP in triggering autoreactivity by presentation of them to T-cells which then orchestrate a cascade of autoimmune reactions directed against CNS myelin (100). (4) Detection of MBP and also anti-MBP in sera and CSF of MS patients and also indication of correlation between degree of this auto-antibody and severity of disease (101, 102). On the other hand, Traugott et al. (103) treated Strain 13 guinea pigs with chronic relapsing experimental autoimmune (allergic) encephalomyelitis (EAE) induced by a single sensitization with whole spinal cord at different stages of the disease with injection containing either MBP alone in incomplete Freund's adjuvant (IFA), or MBP in combination with a lipid hapten of myelin, galactocerebroside in IFA. Although previous studies have been suggested that presence of MBP and galactocerebroside is necessary for sensitization of T cells and production of anti-myelin antibodies, respectively, injection of MBP and galactocerebroside together can induce extensive remyelination and oligodendroglial proliferation in CNS lesions which is accompanying with clinical improvement has been noted with little or no development of relapses over an follow-up period of more than one year post-treatment.

Conclusion remarks

Taken together, our findings suggested that although autoantibodies and cytokines with inflammatory effects play an important role in MS pathogenesis, there are unique repertoires of autoantibodies and

cytokines with remyelinating and dual role in MS patients. Furthermore, our investigation suggested that although plasmapheresis is used as a common treatment for MS patients during relapsing phase, further studies should be undertaken to determine levels and exact effects of beneficial components in sera of MS patients during different phase of disease and then an appropriate protocol should be designed based on levels of special markers including both beneficial and harmful types of them in blood of MS patients.

Conflict of interest

None.

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